

Morena Tartari
University of Antwerp

Being a mother and a transnational researcher amid Covid-19 crisis

This short article reflects on my experience as a transnational researcher during the early months of the Covid-19 outbreak (January–April 2020). I utilize the sociological approach of Institutional Ethnography to analyse and discuss what I observed from my standpoint and to draw some conclusions about the possibilities and impossibilities of the Covid-19 pandemic for mothers who are transnational researchers.

Before presenting and discussing my observations, I briefly explain the definition of transnational researcher that I utilize and the Institutional Ethnography approach.

The literature about the topic of transnational researchers is scant, and it does not fit the specific situation that I shall analyse. I propose to define a *transnational researcher* as a social actor whose work, personal and family life are framed by different institutions, like states, funding agencies and universities, in different countries at the same time.

In connection to my personal experience, these institutions have been the governments (including governmental agencies like health agencies and primary schools) of four different countries (Belgium, Italy, Spain and the UK) where I conducted my fieldwork, the universities that hosted my project and its fieldwork, and the European Commission, which funded my grant. Having been born and lived in Italy until August 2019, in September 2019, to start my research project funded by a Marie Skłodowska-Curie Individual Fellowship (author's name), I migrated to Belgium, where the host institution of my project is located, and took up residence there with my 8-year-old son. While the Covid-19 crisis was beginning (January–April 2020), I was with my son in Edinburgh (UK) for a phase of my research project.

For the analysis I present here, I utilized the approach of Institutional Ethnography (IE) developed by Smith (Smith 2005; 2006) and reformulated by Campbell and Gregor (2002) and McCoy (2008). IE is an empirical investigation of the linkages among local settings of everyday life, organizations, and the translocal processes of administration and governance. The notion of 'institution' does not refer to a type of organization, but rather to clusters of text-mediated relations organized around particular ruling functions, for instance, education or healthcare. IE investigates a defined section of the social world from the *standpoint* of the organization of the work of individuals, and it concentrates on their concrete experience. IE's commitment is to identify problems of everyday life and the ruling relations, and it focuses on the *disjunctures* between individuals' experience and the ruling perspective of the institutions. With the term 'ruling relations', Smith (1999) denotes a complex field of coordination and control of people's local experience.

In this article, I reflect on the *disjunctures* between the different versions of reality (my experiential perspective versus the ruling perspectives of the various institutions that framed my experience at different stages) from my standpoint as an international researcher, a woman and a single mother.

My analysis is based on entries from my diary, articles and videos from the mass media, posts on social media (by academic and personal contacts), and institutional texts (e.g., regulations, policies).

From my standpoint—as a transnational researcher, a woman and a single mother—I could observe how the ruling relations of the following countries affected the organization of my work and personal life when the Covid-19 crisis emerged: 1) Italy, where my parents live and where one

of my fieldworks was active; 2) Belgium, where I took up residence and my host institution and the fieldwork were located; 3) the UK, where I was living for the secondment phase of my fellowship and the fieldwork for my research project; and 4) Spain, where I had planned moved in June 2020 to start the fieldwork. My practices of mothering and transnationally researching were ruled, at the same time, by the European Union Research Agency and by different institutions of these four countries (e.g., academic institutions and governmental agencies and their bureaucratic organization). The mass media are also among these institutions because the texts that they produced had a role in ruling people's reactions and governments' measures.

The onset of the Covid-19 crisis was followed by marked differences among the four countries of my research fieldwork and the actions of their governments in terms of restrictive measures and reaction times from the first announced case. The first lockdowns were decreed on February 21st in Italy, March 18th in Belgium, March 23rd in the UK, and March 17th in Spain. Many universities anticipated the lockdown by some days or weeks with respect to their national governments, switching courses from in-presence to online. At the same time, schools (like the primary school attended by my son in Edinburgh) started their closure after the universities. Later, when we finally left Scotland on May 30th where schools and universities were closed and many restrictive measures were still in place, we came back to Belgium where schools reopened on June 1st, regulations were not requiring wearing masks in public places and supermarkets, and people gathered at cafes seemed to be not worried about the infection. At that time, in Italy, people were preparing to go to summer holidays without major restrictions. However, in the Spanish area where my fieldwork should have been done, restrictions were in place, the university was still closed, and they did not accept my planned visit.

Governments and institutions ruled my research activities and my personal and family life in different countries at the same time. This may sound obvious in 'normal' times, but the different reactions of these institutions (in terms of timing and measures) to the Covid-19 outbreak affected the ongoing and future activities and expectations of myself, of my research participants (single mothers and professionals), and of all transnational researchers who, in particular, were parents and single parents.

First, I observed that I experienced a disjuncture in my daily life between how media influenced our reactions to the virus threat and how governments and institutions ruled our behaviours. This happened in a translocal dimension. For example, while the mass media and social media disseminated videos and posts about the high increase of deaths in northern Italy, in the UK our daily life proceeded as normal. This disjuncture between the media representations of the Covid-19 threat and those by the government induced people to decide on their own about their personal and family safety. For example, parents in the area where I lived decided themselves to keep their children at home before the government decided to close schools. On the other hand, schools told parents that this kind of absence was not justified until a decision was made by the government.

Therefore, in a vacuum of ruling preventive measures by the UK government and by my university (which has no regulatory power at a local level in the UK), I found myself having to decide which of the institutional discourses circulating transnationally in those weeks I had to follow. I name them the 'stay-at-home' and the 'go-ahead' discourses because for some weeks they represented two opposing ways in which institutions reacted to the Covid-19 outbreak. I decided to comply with the local regulations: I continued to work outside the home until the University of Edinburgh's closure, and my son went to school until its official closure. However, I received messages from Italian colleagues and friends who accused me of being irresponsible.

On March 15th, my son, who had been attending school in Edinburgh uninterruptedly from the beginning of January, was bullied by his classmates for being an Italian "who brings the infection

to Scotland". This discourse on the 'guilty other' was a consequence of the representations circulating in the media about the dynamics of and responsibilities for the international spread of the infection. It is possible that children were experiencing the disjuncture between the media discourse on the Covid-19 threat and the initial 'go-ahead' discourse by the UK government. Moreover, in many situations, I experienced a disjuncture in my daily life between the actual needs of my family as a single parent and the ruling relations that framed my family and research activities.

From March 20th onwards, I was a transnational researcher working online at our temporary Scottish home and single in mothering a child in home-schooling at a Scottish primary school 'until further notice'. At the same time, I needed to switch all fieldwork of my project from face-to-face to online mode because from a certain point of the Covid-19 emergency outbreak, participants in the countries envisaged for my fieldwork were locked down at home (many with children at home like me). From April 2020, I needed to return to Belgium at the end of my research phase in Scotland, and I needed to consider different, discordant and international texts that regulated my international journey (from the UK, through Holland, to Belgium) with a child during a pandemic. Furthermore, while some countries activated national schemes for paid postponements of postdoc research projects to cope with delays due to the Covid-19 crisis, the situation for MSC fellows was different. The possibilities offered by the EU were or an unpaid suspension of the projects for the months of the lockdown or the passage from a full-time to a part-time contract. As a parent (with rents to pay for my homes in Belgium and Scotland), I was not in a situation to suspend or reduce my salary. I started working during the night and home-schooling during the day.

Finally, when we left Scotland on May 30th, Italy and Belgium were rapidly improving and they claimed, through mass media, for a quick recovery after the pandemic, while the mass media drew on UK responsibilities in worsening. When I re-started working from Belgium on June 1st, I had the direct experience of different and discordant discourses that affected how I could organize my work. The Spanish university declined my visit due to the preventive measures. My Scottish fieldwork ended without the possibility of interviewing parents due to the lockdown; however, the Belgian and Italian institutions allowed me to re-start the research (even in person if I had liked it), while my son attended the Belgian school that reopened with reduced hours. Rules and preventive measures seemed to be not harmonized among and within countries, and many doubts and uncertainties arose about how to organize and harmonize my work and daily life within a time horizon of a few days.

My analysis highlights how institutions tried to transform the Covid-19 virus into a text, generating competition between different texts in interpreting the virus's existence. These competing interpretations tried to gain power over the virus and people by ruling the lives of different social groups. Some examples of these competitions come from my research fieldwork and in first-person experience, as follows. First, the lockdown measures were not applied to parents who shared their children's custody, causing a lack of protection for people in the 'at-risk' category and showing that family rights come before health rights (stated by the 'stay-at-home' discourse). Secondly, in the same country and town (i.e., the UK and Edinburgh, where I lived when the Covid-19 crisis emerged), organizations like universities, government, council and schools ruled parents' at-home work and children's schools closing (offering competing interpretations of the virus' dangerousness) differently. Then, the 'stay-at-home' measures appeared to be gender-insensitive in the absence of ad hoc policies for women. Health discourses seemed to prevail on the rights to work, particularly affecting single mothers' incomes. Several examples of these effects of the competing interpretations of the virus come from my fieldwork.

I conclude by arguing that the analysis of these *disjunctures* highlights some impossibilities imposed by the Covid-19 crisis on transnational researchers and parents, in particular single parents. The Covid-19 crisis has made many pre-existing problematics (using an IE's term) more visible. If many of these impossibilities were caused by the nature of the Covid-19 virus itself (like its uncertain development), other impossibilities were structural and ruled by the institutions.

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